

Title	Author(s)	Conference/Journal	Year	Size	Language	RQ1: Which Tools?	RQ1: Tool Type	RQ2: Validation Methods?	RQ2: How many people?	RQ3: Which Objectives?	RQ3: Proposal	RQ4: Which Subject?	RQ5: Still available?	RQ6: Link	RQ6: Which kind of VI?	RQ7: Future work?	Where it was proposed to be used?
A framework for automatic text-to-flowchart conversion: A novel teaching aid for novice programmers	D. Hooshyar, R. B. Ahmad and M. H. N. M. Nasir	2014 International Conference on Computer, Control, Informatics and Its Applications	2014	Short (6)	English	Unnamed Text-to-flowchart Conversion Between Framework	Conceptual Framework	Validation with experts analysing applicability and accuracy of the framework. Não há protótipo. O artigo não informou como foi a avaliação. Com resultados, os dados que os experts acharam o trabalho válido e preciso. Resultado: Informal evaluation not explained	7 experts	The main objective of this research is to develop a framework to improve the solution designing and problem-solving skills in novice programmers for both sighted and blind users.	novel conceptual framework which will provide text in English words converted to its corresponding flowchart with getting notices involved in flowchart drawing	Programming / Flowchart Making	Prototype hadn't even been developed software was not finished by the time the article was written	-	Blind users Sighted and blind users	The implementation of our proposed framework as a software prototype as well as its evaluation by conducting an experimental study using novices.	In an attempt to solve school level programming problems. This framework is able to make teaching programming subjects a more appealing option for teachers and learners. Result: Academia
A Java programming tool for students with visual disabilities	Ann C. Smith, Joan M. Francioni, and Sam D. Matzek	ASSETS' 00: The 4th ACM SIGCAPH Conference on Assistive Technologies	2000	Full (7)	English	JavaSpeak (prototype)	Specialized Programming Environment (similar to an IDE)	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Help students learn the connection between the syntax of the language and the semantics of the language.	JavaSpeak is an editor with aural feedback designed to provide a user with useful information about the program's structure and semantics. It is designed to parse the program and "speak" the program's structure to a blind user.	Java Programming / IDE Creation	Yes (Dead Link)	http://www.cs.cornell.edu/~annsmith/JavaSpeak/	Blind and Visually Impaired users; Students with visual disabilities	Work with programmers who have a visual disability in using the JavaSpeak prototype and add features (ex.: debugging support)	The tool is meant to be used by computer science majors learning the programming language Java. Result: Academia
A JBrick: Accessible Robotics Programming for Visually Impaired Users	Ludi, S., Jordan, S.	International Conference on Universal Access in Human-Computer Interaction - UAHCI 2015	2015	Full (12)	English	JBrick	Software Implemented in Java (desktop sys)	Informal experiment: they used JBrick between 3-4 h per day over the course of 4 days e depois responderam um Semi-structured interview, short online survey.	10 VI teenager participants ranging from moderate vision impairments to completely blind	Devise accessible Lego Mindstorms programming software that can be used by those with or without sight.	enable the participants to explore Computer Science via robotics, a common vehicle for engaging pre-college students	Robotics	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Further studies in order to improve the user experience for novice programmers who are blind. Implement additional features in order to provide students the ability to navigate code using audio cues, as well as debugging. Provide Mac OSX support. In addition, JBrick will be revised to accommodate the new version of Lego Mindstorms (EV3), as changes to the compiler are likely.	teens who are visually impaired. Result: high school
A novel E-learning framework to learn IT skills for visual impaired	K. V. K. Kishore and A. Raghunath	1st International Conference on Futuristic trend in Computational Analysis and Knowledge Management (ABLAZE-2015)	2015	Short (5)	English	Unnamed E-learning environment	Web system (java)	Questionnaire, closed questions (tzeram um informal evaluation)	30 visually impaired students	Create an E-learning system that provides quality interaction between visually impaired user and the e-learning platform.	This work is mostly focused on the issue of web accessibility and to facilitate effective access of content and learning to the visually-impaired students.	Information Technology	Not shown in the article	-	Visually Impaired users	Carry out similar development for more courses.	IT related courses Result: schools or universities (nao focu claro), mas não é indústrias
Accessible AST-Based Programming for Visually-Impaired Programmers	Emmanuel Schanzer, Sina Bahram, and Shiram Krishnamurthi	50th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education - SIGCSE' 19	2019	Full (7)	English	CodeMirror-Blocks	Toolkit, Browser-Only (JavaScript)	Experiment: Tasks given to participants and questions about their experience. Comparison between CMB as the experiment and a browser textarea element as the control	13 blind programmers	our tool allows for navigation and editing of code	Present a new toolkit for building fully-accessible programming environments for multiple languages.	block based Programming	Not shown in the article	https://github.com/emmanuel-schanzer/codemirror-blocks	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Focus on the editing functionality. Evaluate the tool when examining languages with which the users are already familiar. More robust search feature, a "glances" stack to save the current position. Explore the impact of using CMB as an IDE for sighted users.	Não tá claro, mas usaram programadores na avaliação. Minha inferência é que serve pra qualquer cenário
Accessible Blockly: An Accessible Block-Based Programming Library for People with Visual Impairments	Aboubakar Mountapbeme, Obianuju Okafor, and Stephanie Ludi	24th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility - ASSETS '22	2022	Full (15)	English	Accessible Blockly	Programming Library	Experiment: evaluation study comparing between Accessible Blockly vs. Blockly's	12 blind programmers	Make the Blockly library accessible through a screen reader and keyboard	Accessible Blockly maintains the same visual and mouse-based interaction as the original Blockly and uses WAI-ARIA guidelines [12] to add screen reader and keyboard interactions. Accessible Blockly is a natural extension to Blockly	block based Programming	Yes (used in article)	https://github.com/aboubakar-mountapbeme/accessible-blockly	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Updating the screen reader output by improving the verb descriptions and increasing the amount and type of information a user would get through the screen reader	Não tá claro, mas usaram programadores na avaliação. Minha inferência é que serve pra qualquer cenário
Accessible Circuit Diagrams	E. C. Pender and J. Healy	2022 33rd Irish Signals and Systems Conference (ISSC)	2022	Short (6)	English	NetListToText / Tangible Tool	Software Solution / Tactile Solution	Informal evaluation through survey	10 blind and 7 visually impaired volunteers	Make circuit schematics more accessible to visually impaired and blind students.	It was designed to comprehensively describe nodal connections, such that the circuit description is used as a substitute for the equivalent graphical representation in academic material. By accessing the circuit descriptions in the alttext of circuit diagrams, screen readers may interpret previously inaccessible information.	Electric Circuits	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Developing the tactile solution further by using blocks similar to lego blocks, incorporate NetListToText as an add-on to LTSPICE such that the circuit descriptions are generated automatically	to support a student pursuing an undergraduate degree in Electronic and Electrical Engineering. Result: pra ser usado na academia
Ambient Intelligence System Enabling People With Blindness to Develop Electrotechnical Components and Their Drivers	M. Hudec and Z. Smutny	IEEE Access - IEEE Education Society Section	2022	Full (27)	English	AMI System RUDDO	Ambient Intelligence System	Qualitative Research and Cognitive Walkthrough	Qualitative evaluation with 1 blind programmer	Broaden the knowledge base by the principles of involving people with blindness in the development and construction of electrotechnical components (or prototypes).	he designed technological procedures enable people with blindness to carry out tasks concerning the development of electrotechnical components and their drivers	Electrotechnical Components / Hardware	A video of the usage	https://zenodo.org/record/5876542	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Replace the setup by a mobile phone with pre-installed modules of the RUDD system which would need to be adjusted to the relevant operating system of the mobile phone that would offer wireless communication with the multimeter and the oscilloscope. Software converting a text file into a graphically expressed circuit scheme with a possible design of a printed circuit board.	computer education. Result: sugere o uso na academia
An Initial Investigation into Non-visual Code Structure Overview Through Speech, Non-speech and Sparscore	Joe Hutchinson and Oussama Meftali	CHI EA'18: Extended Abstracts of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	2018	Short (8)	English	ACONT (Auditory Code Overview and Navigation Tool)	Navigation Tool	Informal evaluation using the tool and feedback survey	10 sighted and 3 non-sighted participants	Develop an alternative way for code reading aside from screen readers	non-visual approach to overviewing object-oriented source code and evaluate the efficiency of different categories of sounds for the purpose of getting an overview of source code structure for a visually-impaired compiler programmer. The tool supports the task of a programmer quickly scrolling through a class file in order for them to gain a quick understanding of its structure.	Programming	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Não tá claro, mas usaram programadores na avaliação. Minha inferência é que serve pra qualquer cenário	
APL: Audio Programming Language for Blind Learners	Sánchez, J., Aguayo, F.	ICCHP 2006 - International Conference on Computers for Handicapped Persons	2006	Full (8)	English	APL (Audio Programming Language)	Java code generator	Informal Qualitative study	3 not blind experts and 3 blind novice programming learners	Allow blind people to construct programs and solve problems with increasingly complexity.	for blind learners based on audio interfaces to support novice blind learners to develop and exercise problem solving skills.	Programming Language	Not shown in the article	-	Blind users	Further studies	to motivate blind learners to enter to the programming world. Não tá claro, mas usaram programadores na avaliação. Minha inferência é que serve pra qualquer cenário
ApreNDER: Ferramenta de apoio à construção de diagrama entidade relacionamento para deficientes visuais	Magalhães, Rafael L., and Michele MF Neto	XXI Simpósio Brasileiro de Informática na Educação	2010	Full (10)	Portuguese	ApreNDER	Software in Delphi	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Include visually impaired students in the same condition as the other students and facilitate the teacher's job in special education.	ferramenta ApreNDER, implementada com um menu interativo em áudio combinado a operações no teclado, permitindo ao deficiente visual criar um Diagrama Entidade Relacionamento (DER)	Diagrams / Entity-Relationship Diagram	Not shown in the article	-	Visually Impaired users	Turn ApreNDER into a free tool with more graphical support, make a web-based version to allow to have a bigger reach and expand it to other areas like math and physics.	Academia
Autlograf: a diagram-reader for the blind	Andrea R. Kennel	Assets '96: Proceedings of the second annual ACM conference on Assistive technologies	1996	Short (8)	English	AudioGraf	Diagram-reader	Informal Usability tests	Not specified	Enable blind and visually impaired people to read technical reports and papers interrelations that are often represented as diagrams.	AudioGraf is a diagram-reader which represents simple diagrams in an audio-tactile way	Diagrams	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and visually impaired users	Further tests have to be done to find an effective auditory display to optimize the readability.	Minha inferência é que serve pra qualquer cenário
AudioHighlight: Code Skimming for Blind Programmers	A. Armaly, P. Rodeghiero and C. Nicklman	ICSMSE 2018 - IEEE International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution	2018	Full (11)	English	AudioHighlight	Web service and a Eclipse plugin	Formal evaluation: an experiment - A comparison study with the current state of the art tools	10 experienced blind programmers	Enable code navigation on the web.	The audiohighlight webservice is responsible for marking up the source code to make it possible for a blind programmer to skim the code structure. The purpose of the Audiohighlight plugin is to provide a code skimming interface for the Eclipse IDE.	Programming / Code Skimming	Maybe on Eclipse	?	Blind users	-	blind programmers. Não fala de alunos. Result: Foco na indústria
Automated Interpretation and accessible presentation of technical diagrams for blind people	Horstmann*, Mirko, et al.	New Review of Hypertexts and Multimedia (journal)	2004	Full (24)	English	TeDUB (Technical Drawings and Multimedia for the Blind)	Software system	participants were asked to read different types of UML diagrams and answer Questionnaire with Likert Scale	35 participants (they did not inform if they were blind or not)	To make technical diagrams accessible to blind and visually impaired people.	The system is capable of generating technical diagrams from a number of formally defined domains.	Diagrams	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and visually impaired users	The two central points of future work are widening the scope of the tool and representing the "meaning" of graphics	estudantes e profissionais participaram de avaliação. Result: eu diria qualquer cenário.
B-Model Uma ferramenta para auxiliar estudantes com deficiência visual na modelagem de sistemas	de Azevedo, Pedro, Francisco Carlos Souza, and Alaine Souza	Revista Eletrônica De Iniciação Científica Em Computação	2021	Full (15)	Portuguese	B-Model / BML	Software Python using Spacy and Tkinter	informal case study and GQM application	3 estudantes com deficiência visual	Assist visually impaired students on solution modeling activity supported by Unified Modeling Language (UML).	Para viabilizar o uso da ferramenta B-Model foi desenvolvida uma linguagem chamada Blind Modeling Language(BML), para padronizar a especificação, to de requisitos a fim de facilitar a gerac, ao autom atica de diagramas de caso de uso.	Diagrams / UML	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Evaluate the BML language with more students, add the indice and search relationships, validate the tool with students.	estudantes Result: academia
Bank: accessible programming for accessible audio games	Shaun K. Kane, Varsha Koushik, and Annika Muehlbradt	IDC '18: Proceedings of the 17th ACM Conference on Interaction Design and Children	2018	Full (11)	English	Bank	Programming environment (JavaScript)	Workshop experience with students (informal evaluation)	10 students	Create a programming tool to create accessible and shareable media.	an accessible programming environment that enables the creation of interactive audio games using a subset of the JavaScript programming language.	Game Development	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and visually impaired users	Expand the tool to allow it to create accessible media in general	teh evaluation was with high school students. Result: academia

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CodeTalk: Improving Programming Environment Accessibility for Visually Impaired Developers	Venkatesh Paduri, Priyan Vaidyanathan, Manohar Swaminathan, and Gopal Srinivasa	CHI '18: Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	2018	Full (11)	English	CodeTalk	Plugin for Visual Studio	preliminary Exploratory study, Participant solicitation, user study without and with CodeTalk, and post user study with an online survey	6 blind participants	Create a way to ensure blind developers of taking full advantage of the IDE they are currently using	Our approach is to minimize the effort of the VI developer actively seeking information by proactive extraction and presentation of information or by introducing an audio channel distinct from the screen reader. CodeTalk extracts the information relevant to the context and makes it accessible to the developer with reduced effort.	Programming / IDE	Yes	https://github.com/visually-impaired/code-talk	Blind and visually impaired users	Devise new techniques that can gently induce the user to discover features when it's most useful.	-nao deixo claro. Result: eu diria outro centro.
deficiencia.org: Relato Sobre o Emprego de Ferramentas Computacionais Enquanto Tecnologias Assistivas no Ensino/Aprendizagem Para Pessoas com Deficiência Visual	Reis, Louise Suelen Araújo, and Vânia Cordeiro da Silva	Anais do XXX Workshop sobre Educação em Computação (WEI 2022)	2022	Full (12)	Portuguese	deficiencia.org	Website (Ruby on Rails & JavaScript)	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Create a practical initiative of compiling contents of interest from other students with any sort of disability as well as teachers from the sciences and technologies areas.	This work presents a website developed by a blind computer science student. O site for criação para compartilhar aulas, materiais acessíveis, artigos e tudo que possa vir a colaborar com a inclusão das pessoas com deficiência	Programming / Online CS Classes	No (Dead Link)	deficiencia.org	Low vision and blind users	Increasingly encompass the construction and dissemination of computer science-oriented content.	-Tendo como público-alvo, alunos com deficiências. Result: academia
Developing methodologies for the presentation of graphical educational material in a non-visual form for use by people with vision impairment	N. Mohammadi and I. Murray	IEEE International Conference on Teaching, Assessment and Learning for Engineering (TALE)	2013	Short (5)	English	Accessible Packet Tracer	accessible version of Packet Tracer	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Improve accessibility in graphical presentation of educational information of Cisco Networking Academy content.	By using this accessible version of Packet Tracer students with vision impairments are able to interact with network simulator in the same way as sighted students.	Network / Cisco Packet Tracer	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and visually impaired users	Testing the program including accessibility of Netsim interface, response time, accuracy of the program, and PT Diagnostics query and response.	for students. Result: academia
Drawing and Understanding Diagrams: An Accessible Approach Dedicated to Blind People	Serin, F., Romeo, K	HCI 2022: Universal Access in Human-Computer Interaction, User and Context Diversity	2022	Full (16)	English	Latitude (Light and Accessible Tags into plain text using Universal Design)	Software that creates HTML and SVG files from plain text	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Enable collaboration between blind and sighted people, which means inclusion and accessibility.	we focus on the design and reading of class diagrams according to the UML standard. It allows, from a plain text enriched with light and nonintrusive tags to automatically generate documents in HTML format and in SVG format.	UML	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Test the tool with young blinds learning CS, develop use case diagrams, bar and pie charts.	-nao deixo claro. Result: eu diria outro centro.
Ferramentas para Mediação do Processo de Desenvolvimento do Pensamento Algorítmico contemplando Precalços de Acessibilidade	SANTOS, Cristina Prado; AJALA, Vinícius; SILVA, Denilson da	VIII Congresso Brasileiro de Informática na Educação (CBIE 2019) Anais do XXV Workshop de Informática na Escola (WIE 2019)	2019	Short (8)	Portuguese	CEEduc	Software written in Java	Usage Scenarios	5 researchers/teachers	Support the process of algorithmic thinking development and to concretize principles of equity promoting spaces of sociological mediation for blind individuals.	Envolveu a incorporação de recursos de acessibilidade baseados no sistema TTS (Text To Speech) que transforma um texto simples em voz.	Algorithm Thinking	Not shown in the article	-	Blind users	Studies in this sense are being developed with a view to contemplating resources such as a magnifying glass, high contrast, color resolution and font editing, thus expanding the potential for interaction in the construction of knowledge. In addition, an evaluation of the tool with blind students should also be carried out.	Para a avaliação dos recursos de acessibilidade contemplados nas ferramentas, contou-se com a participação de 5 avaliadores sendo 2 deles docentes alunas na disciplina de Interação Humano-Computador. Result: Academia
Grid-Coding: An Accessible, Efficient, and Structured Coding Paradigm for Blind and Low-Vision Programmers	Md Ehtesham-Ul-Haque, Syed Mostafa Monwar, and Syed Masum Bilal	ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology (UIST '22), October 23-November 2, 2022, Bend, OR, USA	2022	Full (21)	English	Grid-Coding	Programming paradigm	Within-subject design quantitative study	12 blind or low vision programmers	Make reading and writing of mainstream programming to edit a Statement or to create a new one (namely, mutate the AST).	Abstract Syntax Table (ASTab) maintains the proposed grid structure and allows programmers to build machine learning models in Python, investigate whether or how Grid-Coding can benefit low-vision programmers who use screen magnifiers during programming.	Programming / Code Navigation	Yes No (Dead-Link)	https://ui.st.acm.org/2022/program/program-106	Blind and Low Vision users	Integrate Grid Editor with Jupyter Notebook to allow BLV programmers to build machine learning models in Python, investigate whether or how Grid-Coding can benefit low-vision programmers who use screen magnifiers during programming.	These participants used our prototype in their daily coding activities (e.g., doing homework, copying and pasting 3rd-party code to check the overall structure, and for fun). From time to time, they provided feedback, reported bugs, and requested new features via emails. Result: Industry
GUIDL as an Aiding Technology in Programming Education of Visually Impaired	Konecki, Mario	Journal of Computers	2014	Short (6)	English	GUIDL	Description Language and System	Tests with the use of the tool and a questionnaire	32 visually impaired participants	Develop a suitable mean for aiding visually impaired in their programming education.	Graphical User Interface Description Language (GUIDL) system is proposed as a suitable mean for aiding visually impaired in their programming education.	Programming	Not shown in the article	-	Visually Impaired users	Adding new features and expanding its possible areas.	The results of given tasks solving indicate that GUIDL system is indeed suitable for programming novices education and that it is also suitable as an aiding technology in graphical user interface creation for visually impaired. Result: Industry
How Can Java Be Made Blind-Friendly	Markus, Norbert, et al.	Computers Helping People with Special Needs, ICCHP 2008. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 5105. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-76540-6_75	2008	Full (8)	English	Mobile State Talker (MOST)	Java-based GUI-free man-machine interface	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Eliminate the need of any screen reader to code in Java.	Java powered blind-friendly environment mainly used on PDA, pocket computers. It provides the most essential inbuilt applications and a plug-in loading capability to load any number of Java plug-ins that may be developed by anyone.	Programming Environment	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Localization for other languages.	Not mentioned in the paper
Including blind people in computing through access to graphs	Suzanne P. Balk, Sean P. Mealin, Matthias F. Stallmann, Robert D. Roodman, Michelle L. Glitz, and Veronica J. Sigler	ASSETS '14: Proceedings of the 16th International ACM SIGACCESS conference on Computers & accessibility, October 2014, Pages 91–98https://doi.org/10.1145/2561134.2561164	2014	Full (8)	English	Graph Sketching tool (GSK)	Graph Sketching tool Java application	Graph examination, creation and navigation study	9 blind screen reader users, 3 secondary students, 3 undergraduate students, 2 college graduates, and 1 graduate student)	Provide blind screen reader users with a means to create and access graphs as node-link diagrams and share them with sighted people in real-time.	To provide blind screen reader users with a means to create and access graphs as node-link diagrams and share them with sighted people in real-time.	Graphs	No (Dead Link)	https://assetschi.org/csic/2014/Access3811/SIGACCESS.html	Blind users	Investigate the appeal of GSK for sighted users and make any necessary improvements.	We wanted to determine how well GSK would work for other blind students and recent graduates. We therefore carried out a user study in which blind participants used GSK and Microsoft Excel, as a control, to examine and navigate graphs. They also used GSK to create several graphs. Result: Academia
Learning electronics using image processing techniques for describing circuits to blind students	B. G. Zapirain, A. M. Zorilla, I. Ruiz and A. Muro	ISSPIT '10: Proceedings of the 10th IEEE International Symposium on Signal Processing and Information Technology/December 2010, Pages 156–160https://doi.org/10.1109/ISSPIT.2010.5711764	2010	Short (5)	English	Unnamed open source algorithm: open source algorithm integrated in a tool compatible with OpenOffice	Open source algorithm	Satisfaction survey questionnaire	18 blind people	Implement an algorithm that processes circuits schematics images and provides a textual description of the elements and their content.	They presented open source algorithm integrated in a tool compatible with OpenOffice who applies digital image processing and computer vision techniques to any circuits schematics included in the document and provides an intelligent and automatic textual description of both the sequence of electronic components and the position in the general schematics in order to make it accessible to blind people.	Electronics	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Working into adding more information about the circuit's schematic before starting the description of blocks and text.	The test with final users from Technolade Company demonstrated that the documentation created with Open Office software including their description for schematic circuit's description is totally accessible to blind people. Result: Industry
Lessons and tools from teaching a blind student	Connelly, Richard	Journal of Computing Sciences in Colleges/Volume 29 Issue 6pp 34–39	2010	Short (6)	English	pcspeak.h	Header File	Experience teaching a student	1 blind student	Connect the standard C++ iostreams to eSpeak, an open source text-to-speech system.	The authors reported the experience of teaching a blind computer science major in three courses and part of a fourth. Three courses and part of a fourth were taught across one academic year. The first course was scheduled, but the others were done on short notice due to faculty illness. The first course also differed, because it was "off term and one-to-one. The pcspeak system is one of the few tools for blind programmers.	Programming	No	Only an example	Blind users	Not mentioned in the paper	The student is a computer major who is now blind, but had partial vision into high school. The blind student and another were scheduled to take the course. The plan was to have them work as partners with considerable teacher and tutor support as had been done in Computer Science 1. Result: Academia
Making turing machines accessible to blind students	Pierluigi Crescenzi, Leonardo Rossi, and Gianluca Apollaro	SIGCSE '12: Proceedings of the 43rd ACM technical symposium on Computer Science Education/February 2012, Pages 167–172https://doi.org/10.1145/2157136.2157190	2012	Short (6)	English	Accessible JFLAP	Software	Use of the tool	1 first year blind student	Modify the current version of JFLAP in order to obtain a new version of the TM editor tool which could be used by blind students	One of the main goal of our project was to make the accessible application as much similar as possible to the original one, in order to allow a blind student to cooperate with other sighted students.	Turing Machines	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Validate the software in a more extensive way. Validate the tool from a cooperation point of view, by letting pairs of students (one blind and one sighted) work on it. Extend the accessibility features to the other models and add support for more languages.	TM competition that took place at the University of Pisa, Italy. The first author started teaching the TCS course in the fall semester of 2005. Since 2006 he decided to use a TM simulator in order to define, to exercise, and to debug TMs (instead, from 2006 to 2008 a laboratory exam was also included as part of the final grade). Result: Academia
Model2gether: a tool to support cooperative modeling involving blind people	Luque, Leandro, et al	IME USP/Brazilian Conference of Software	2016	Full (8)	English	Model2gether	Free Software - distributed under the GNU	Case Study	4 blinds and 1 sighted user	Support the inclusion of blind people in cooperative modeling.	Web-based tool that support the inclusion of blind people in cooperative modeling.	Diagrams / UML	No (Dead Link)	http://www.model2gether.com.br/	Blind users	Implementing new models, implement new features, such as support for tactile devices, DSL, customizations, and coordination mechanisms. Furthermore, experiments with more users will be conducted.	The interface for sighted users shows use case models in their diagrammatic format and interaction is possible through mouse and keyboard. A model may be shared with other participants through a sharing option, shown in the main interface. In all use case models owned by the user or shared with him/her are shown. Result: Academia

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ModelByVoice - towards a general purpose model editor for blind people	Lopes, João, João Cambeiro, and Vasco Amaral	VII CONGRESSO BRASILEIRO DE SOFTWARE: TEORIA E PRÁTICA (CIBSOFT 2016) - SESSÃO DE FERRAMENTAS: MatringVolume: 1	2018	Full (8)	English	ModelByVoice	Tool Prototype	Preliminary assessment and questionnaire	2 blind people	Provide accessibility to the modeling activity that can be reached both for blind people (and with problems with vision) and users without physical limitations.	They present a prototype of a tool that aims to take advantage of current voice recognition and speech synthesis to edit models in diverse modeling languages. The elegance of this work is the fact that not only it is meant to make MDD accessible to a broader spectrum of practitioners, but also it is developed with an MDD approach.	Diagrams	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Giving the users the possibility to choose the input resource that they intend to use to practice the modeling activity, introduction of an intermediate speech recognition platform independent layer, that would support any speech recognition API.	This tool was used mainly to embed the types of modeling language elements that are to be modeled, in which the data structure chosen to store this information were two lists, one for the nodes and another for the links, thus generating the program code adapted to that modeling language, and which restricts the user to the language domain. Result: Academia
NetAnimations Mobile App: Improvement of Accessibility and Usability to Computer Network Learning Animations	A. R. Svagan and L. A. F. Marfins	IEEE Latin America Transac. on Systems (Volume: 16, Issue: 1, January 2018)	2018	Full (7)	Portuguese	NetAnimations	Computer Network Animation Mobile App	Online forms and a checklist of the WCAG recommendations	12 sighted users and 1 visually impaired user	Formulate a teaching application for the discipline of Computer Networks for mobile devices.	To cooperate with other sighted students.	Network	Yes	https://pub.com/doi/10.1109/latinsys.2017.8144444	Visually Impaired users	Study and propose solutions for the limitations encountered, carrying out assessments with a larger and more diverse audience, and also expanding the application's accessibility levels for deficiencies not yet met, such as motor and hearing impairments.	The objective is to present the formulation, development and evaluation of accessibility and usability in a teaching application for the discipline of Computer Networks for mobile devices. Result: Academia
Node-read: a visually accessible low-code software development extension	Lachlan Anderson, Briana Barker, Alice Reid, Kaiji Lin, Hourieh Khalajzadeh, and John Grundy	ACM/IEEE 25th International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems (MODELS '22 Companion), October 23-28, 2022, Montreal, QC, Canada	2022	Full (8)	English	Node-Read	Extension of an open source software, Node-RED	Use of the tool and questionnaire	11 sighted participants simulating a visual impairment and 1 visually impaired participant	Allow more people with visual impairments to use software development tools.	To making citizen-end-user software development accessible for users who are reliant on screen readers.	IDE / Programming	Removed-for-blind-review	https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.12345	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Further research into the visual accessibility of Node-RED, implementation of accessibility labels that provide context, descriptions and state information for buttons and nodes that are currently referred to in generic terms.	Focuses on improving compatibility with JAWS and NVDA screen readers. The research environment was set up to use the NVDA screen reader for all experiments to ensure that the research environment was consistent and replicable. Researchers watched and recorded participants through the tasks. Result: Academia
Nonvisual tool for navigating hierarchical structures	Ann C. Smith, Justin S. Cook, Joan M. Francini, Adel Hossain, Mohd Anwar, and M. Fayezur Rahman	ACM SIGACCESS Accessibility and Computing Issue 77-78 Sept. 2003 - Jan. 2004 pp. 133-139 https://doi.org/10.1145/1028014.102865/ASSET?	2003	Full (7)	English	Aural Tree Navigator	Plug-in to the Eclipse IDE	Use of the tool and feedback from the participants	10 sighted participants simulating a visual impairment and 2 visually impaired participant	The development of a tool that supports nonvisual navigation, via keyboard input and speech/heard output, of hierarchical representations (or "trees") of information.	They defined a set of requirements for an accessible tree navigation strategy.	IDE / Hierarchical Structures	Not shown in the article	-	Blind users	Extending the implementation to provide a mechanism for users to build their own trees.	An implementation of this strategy was developed as a plug-in to the Eclipse IDE and was tested by twelve student programmers. Result: Academia
On the design of an educational infrastructure for the blind and visually impaired in computer science	Andreas M. Stefan, Christopher Hundhausen, and Derrick Smith	SIGCSE '11: Proceedings of the 42nd ACM technical symposium on Computer science education March 2011 Pages 571-578 https://doi.org/10.1145/1953163.1953334	2011	Short (6)	English	SoBeans / Hop	Auditory programming environment / Programming language	Empirical study (Workshop) with research questions, results were calculated with ANOVA	12 legally blind students	Begin forging a multi-sensory educational infrastructure for the blind across the United States. 1) a new auditory programming environment called SoBeans, a programming language called Hop, and a multi-sensory (sound and touch) curriculum, and 2) an empirical study of our first summer workshop with the blind students.		Programming	Yes	http://doi.org/10.1145/1953163.1953334	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Expanding the program to include more schools for the blind, making regular upgrades and expansions to the software, and working with local and state governments to approve a multi-sensory curriculum that can be put into practice.	Our research attempts to address a broad research challenge: to build a multi-sensory educational infrastructure for the blind and visually impaired across the United States, and to broaden participation in the computer science community in the computing discipline. We conducted an empirical study as part of our first annual summer camp, which had the goal of introducing blind students to computer programming. Result: Academia
Projeto DALL: acesso e manipulação de diagramas por pessoas com deficiência visual	Luciano Tadeu Esteves Pansanato, André Luis Martins Bändera, Luiz Gustavo dos Santos, and Dielson do Prado Perera	IHC '12: Proceedings of the 11th Brazilian Symposium on Human Factors in Computing Systems November 2012 Pages 33-36	2012	Full (10)	Portuguese	DALL	Prototype (Software)	Preemptive survey, tasks and another post survey	12 blind participants	The research, development and extension in the context of approaches and alternative techniques of representation and interaction for access and manipulation of diagrams for people with visual disability.	The project aims to develop assistive technology in the form of computational support to support the proposed alternatives.	UML	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Not mentioned in the paper	O material da avaliação está pronto e a avaliação está em andamento com cerca de 12 participantes. Todos os pesquisadores que trabalham com desenvolvimento de sistemas software. Result: Industry
Remote Laboratory Access for Students with Vision Impairment	I. Murray and H. Armstrong	2009 Fifth International Conference on Networking and Services	2009	Short (6)	English	NetSim	Accessible network simulator	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	NetSim is an accessible network simulator, created to allow both vision-impaired and sighted users to complete CCNA 2 laboratory sessions without access to the networking hardware.		Network	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Not mentioned in the paper	Whilst the use of the remote bundle overcomes many of the limitations imposed by delivering CCNA laboratories to remote blind and vision impaired students, further work is required to improve functionality and ease of use. Result: Academia
StructJumper: A Tool to Help Blind Programmers Navigate and Understand the Structure of Code	Catherine M. Baker, Lauren R. Milne, and Richard E. Ladner	CHI '15: Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems April 2015 Pages 393-395 https://doi.org/10.1145/2702123.2702569	2015	Full (10)	English	StructJumper	Eclipse plugin	Use of the tool and questions about their experiences	7 blind programmers	Allow blind programmers to be able to skim through code easily.	We created StructJumper, a plugin for Eclipse with a hierarchical tree based on the nesting structure of a Java class. The programmer can use the TreeView to get an overview of the code structure of the class (including all the methods and control flow statements) and can quickly switch between the TreeView and the Text Editor to get an idea of where they are within the nested structure.	IDE / Programming	Not shown in the article	-	Blind users	Learn how participants use this tool to perform different coding tasks, research whether this tool is beneficial to sighted programmers and investigate how their use of the tool varies from blind programmers.	To evaluate StructJumper, we had seven blind programmers perform a variety of code exploration tasks both with and without our tool. Results: Industry
TalkSQL: A Tool for the Synthesis of SQL Queries from Verbal Specifications	G. Obaido, A. Ade-Ibija and H. Vadapalli	International Multidisciplinary Information Technology and Engineering Conference (IMITEC)	2020	Full (10)	English	TalkSQL	Voice-based query system	Online survey	52 participants	Use regular expressions into a NLDB system we have designed in this study to find patterns in SQL queries, and provide a comprehensive feedback to a user. The feedback will be available in vocal, textual, and visual forms which will be presented to a user.	The paper introduces a voice-based, conversational NLDB system called TalkSQL, used to aid the comprehension of SQL. TalkSQL is an intelligent, conversational tutoring system that translates natural language queries into an executable SQL query to be used on a test database, and presents an output. Similarly a voice feedback is provided to a learner.	Database	Not shown in the article	-	Visually Impaired users	Integrate and test TalkSQL on a fully fledged database such as Northwind DB, improving the tool to generate feedback for queries with regular forms.	The survey was carried out through an online means, and the feedback was received from 52 participants. Majority of the participants were undergraduate students taking a database course and most of them are familiar with SQL. Results: Academia
Teaching modern object-oriented programming to the blind: An instructor and student experience	Owen, Charles B., Sarah Coburn, and Jordyn Caslor	2014 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition	2014	Full (13)	English	CSpeech / Audible Browser	Drop-in component / Experimental program	Tool Not Properly Evaluated	Tool Not Properly Evaluated	Showcase the tools and methodologies developed to teach a blind student Computer Science.	We have been able to create some simple system extensions to make SoBeans and GDB, the GNU project debugger we utilize in the course, work better together, and we have developed textual, tactile, and audible representations of UML diagrams that are accessible to a blind student.	Programming / UML	No (Dead Link)	http://metab.cse.msu.edu/indiv/oc	Blind users	Not mentioned in the paper	This course represented a unique combination of an instructor who is an expert in multimedia and user interfaces with a student who is highly motivated to learn and succeed. We were able to work together throughout the semester, trying different approaches, learning what worked and discarding what did not. Result: Academia
Teaching the blind to program visually	Siegfried, Robert M., Denis Dikonovskis, and Udochukwu Obianyo-Agu	Information Systems Education Journal Volume 3. http://iseej.org/3/23/ ISSN: 1545-78X	2004	Full (9)	English	Molly.exe	Prototype scripting language	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Provide the blind of what is hoped to be a series of programming tools to help the blind.	To provide a large amount of detailed information about the form's layout when creating Visual Basic forms. The main goal is a scripting language is to simplify the process of designing a form while allowing users to specify property values that differ from the default.	Programming	No (Wrong Link)	http://www.gdsoft.com/~siegfri/m/3/	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Testing the tool with non-sighted users.	After posting the prototype compiler and its manual on Adelphi University's web site (http://www.adelphi.edu/~siegfri/molly/) and notifying members of the Blind Programming mail list of its availability, comments were received about the scripting languages; they indicate that the blind programmers who have read the specifications and the sample scripts believe that it has the potential to help them create Visual Basic forms without the aid of a sighted person. Result: Academia
UML Modeling for Visually-Impaired Persons	Doherty, Brad, and Beth HC Cheng	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119148601.ch01	2015	Full (7)	English	PRISCA	Tool-chain Software	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Facilitate collaborative modeling between VIPs and other project team members.	PRISCA is a project whose overall objective is to facilitate software modeling collaboration between VIP developers and other developers by using tacit representations of software models. PRISCA supports a proof of concept tool-chain that takes output from an existing UML modeling tool and transforms the models into corresponding 3D representations defined in terms of the input language for an existing 3D printer. PRISCA also generates a 3D Braille representation of the textual annotations included in the graphical models.	UML	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Extend PRISCA to handle other diagram types, beyond the sequence and class UML diagrams presented in the paper. Expand PRISCA to address the mentioned research challenges and to facilitate modeling collaboration between VIPs and other development team members. Explore and leverage the emerging technology associated with the use of haptic representations.	Based on review of the literature and feedback from VIP students studying computer science and software engineering, three key obstacles to the graphical artifacts difficult to access by visually-impaired persons (VIPs). Results: Academia

Title	Author(s)	Conference/Journal	Year	Size	Language	RQ1: Which Tools?	RQ1: Tool Type	RQ2: Validation Methods?	RQ2: How many people?	RQ3: Which Objectives?	RQ3: Proposal	RQ4: Which Subject?	RQ5: Still available?	RQ6: Link	RQ6: Which kind of VI?	RQ7: Future work?	Where it was proposed to be used?
UML4ALL Syntax – A Textual Notation for UML Diagrams	Loitsch, C. et al.	International Conference on Computers Helping People with Special Needs, (ICCPH 2018). Computers Helping People with Special Needs pp. 598–605	2018	Full (8)	English	UML4ALL	Syntax	Online questionnaire	14 participants	Facilitate UML-based software development in a cooperative and collaborative manner between people with and without visual impairments.	The UML4ALL syntax supports the way of working of screen reader users, reading content line-by-line with a screen reader by text-to-speech or Braille. The sequential principle is a crucial design choice of the UML4ALL syntax and involves mentioning most important or general information first followed by more specific details. Providing a consistent and clear syntax structure is just as much important to facilitate blind people in understanding the semantics of UML elements as well as finding specific information such as roles or cardinalities.	UML	Yes	https://www.uml4all.net/website/index.html	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Apply the concept developed for UML to other graphs used in common applications, for instance PowerPoint.	The methodology we used for the evaluation was rather difficult because users must familiarize with the UML4ALL syntax by reading a tutorial and afterwards, they were directly required to perform five modeling tasks. Student 3, Researcher 6, Software developer 6. Results: Academia and Industry
Usable and Accessible Robot Programming System for People Who Are Visually Impaired	Damasio Oliveira, J., Campos, M.d.B., Stangerlin Machado Paavo-Cortes, V.	Universal Access in Human-Computer Interaction, Design Approaches and Supporting Technologies, HCI 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 12188. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-330-49282-3_32	2020	Full (20)	English	GoDonnie and Donnie	GoDonnie programming language based and Donnie programming environment	Three studies with different kinds of participants, use of interviews, observation and questionnaire	1 blind participant / 2 visually impaired participants / 16 programming professors	Create an understanding of end-users who are visually impaired.	We developed a robot programming environment based on Logo accessible to PVI. Our strategy is based on teaching programming and the aspects of orientation and mobility (O&M) skills to PVI, which are used to construct representative cognitive maps of different scenarios. O&M skills are necessary for achieving the autonomy of PVI and, consequently, for their independence in different spaces in society. Hence, we have developed a robot programming environment, in which cognitive maps are constructed as the user explores familiar and unfamiliar scenarios through commands that are executed by the robot.	Robotics	Yes	https://github.com/GoDonnie/GoDonnie-robot-eg and https://github.com/GoDonnie/GoDonnie-robot-eg	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Making new assessments with visually impaired people using Module 3. Create a realistic environment (like a classroom) in the virtual environment (Module 2) and, after use, check if the user can move in the real environment. GoDonnie will be enhanced for keyboard input and float, alphabetic, and alphanumeric data types. The COLOR command will review functionality and attributes, as suggested by users.	We evaluated the Donnie programming environment in two steps. In Step 1, which lasted five months, we evaluated the programming language GoDonnie without the environment, the tutorial, and concrete materials developed for the study. Novices and programming experts visually impaired people, and Programming professors participated. This step included teaching the programming language and performing programming activities with increasing levels of difficulty. In Step 2, which lasted two weeks, we evaluated the programming language editor (Module 1) and the 2D simulator (Module 2). It also included performing programming activities and answered a questionnaire. Result: Academia
Using speech and touch to enable blind people to access schematic diagrams	P. Blenkhorn, D.G. Evans	Journal of Network and Computer Applications (1998) 21: 17–20. Article No. ma980060	1998	Full (13)	English	Kevin	CASE tool	Evaluation of hapticons and Comparison of Kevin with tactile diagrams	15 blind participants / 5 blind participants	Develop a system that allows blind users to read, create and edit one type of schematic diagram, namely data flow diagrams used in the Ward-Mellor real-time structured analysis (RTSA) approach.		Diagrams / N' chart	No (Dead Link)	http://www.ci.ccl.uab.cat/~unisa/1998/kyv/n1%23	Blind users	Further evaluation and experimentation is required, and planned, to determine whether the approach offers significant benefits to blind people who wish to access tabular information.	Formal evaluations were carried out in the University of Hertfordshire under the direction of Dr Helen Petre. Result: Academia
WAD: A Feasibility study using the Wicked Audio Debugger	Andrew Stefk, Roger Alexander, Robert Patterson, Jonathan Brown	15th IEEE International Conference on Program Comprehension (ICPC'07)	2007	Full (10)	English	WAD, Wicked Audio Debugger	Debugger for Microsoft Visual Studio 2005	Feasibility study with tasks and a post survey	10 students	find auditory objects that increase a user's dynamic comprehension of computer code without a visual interface.	The Wicked Audio Debugger (WAD), a programming tool designed to assist in debugging the dynamic behavior of computer programs using audio based stimuli.	Programming	Not shown in the article	-	Blind users	Begin collecting data on a series of alternative designs, including musical ones, alternative speech design (designs based on non-English languages, and likely others, also a series of these feasibility studies, we will begin comparative studies with multiple groups using different auditory objects.	Ten students took part in this study, nine were senior level undergraduates and one was a graduate. The experiment lasted approximately one hour. Participants were first given training in the sounds of the auditory objects, where they passively listened to sounds while visually looking at computer code, hopefully making an association. Second, participants completed two practice tasks and, finally, completed the ten tasks for which we present our findings. Results: Academia
Work in Progress Report: Nonvisual Visual Programming	Lewis, Clayton	PIPG, University of Sussex, 2014 www.pipg.org	2014	Short (6)	English	Noodle	Nonvisual dataflow programming system.	Tool Not Evaluated	Tool Not Evaluated	Provide nonvisual access to a dataflow programming system, a popular model for visual programming systems.	Not mentioned in the paper	Programming	Not shown in the article	-	Blind users	Not mentioned in the paper	Not mentioned in the paper
Workspace Awareness Accessive: estratégias de sonificação para projetar interfaces colaborativas acessíveis aos cegos	TORRES, Márcio J. R.; BARWÄLDT, Regina	X Congresso Brasileiro de Informática na Educação (CBIE 2021), Anais do XXVII Simpósio Brasileiro de Informática na Educação (SBIE 2021)	2021	Full (11)	Portuguese	SONv1 / SONv2	Two sonified interfaces	Task oriented study with the use of the tool	3 sighted participants and 3 blind participants	Allow blind users to perceive the interactions of colleagues through sonified interfaces.	Design and evaluate the sonification of events resulting from interactions on shared interfaces. To make it perceptible and discriminable to blind users, strategies were designed to map workspace awareness elements to audible cues reproduced by abstract sounds called Eacorns to signal three events: (a) who is doing it? (b) what are you doing? and (c) where are you doing it?	Diagrams	Not shown in the article	-	Blind and Visually Impaired users	Not mentioned in the paper	Foram recrutados seis participantes para os testes, sendo três visidentes, estudantes do Programa de Pós-graduação em Computação da Universidade Federal do Rio Grande e membros do grupo de pesquisa em Informática na Educação, com experiência em diagramas e questões de usabilidade e acessibilidade, e outros três participantes cegos, alunos de cursos superiores relacionados à área da computação, um com pequena experiência e dois com nenhuma, também com conhecimento sobre informações gramaticais. Result: Academia.
A Method for Presenting UML Class Diagrams with Audio for Blind and Visually Impaired Students	Ira Woodring, Charles Owen, and Sama Islam	PETRA '24: Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments	2024	Short (6)	English	Unnamed Tool	Proof-of-concept of an Auditory Method	Experiment	29 undergraduate students (not defined as vi)	Leverage this mechanism to create a complete class diagramming tool accessible to students who are either blind or visually impaired.	Novel auditory method that conveys relationship properties between classes using sonification techniques.		Still a proof-of-concept	-	All	Future work will be undertaken to create a UML browser that can load pre-created UML diagrams or create diagrams from scratch or existing software source code	Academia
CRAFTPY: allowing people with visual impairments to create diagrams	FRAGA, Lucas Lopes; SANTOS, Rafael Toxiz; ROCHA, Larissa	SBES: Simpósio Brasileiro de Engenharia de Software	2024	Full (7)	English	CraftPy	Accessible web tool	Preliminary Experiment	8 visually impaired participants	Enable SVI to create various types of diagrams using Python code, employing an object-oriented approach to design classes, actors, entities, attributes, and relationships.	Accessible web tool fully compatible with screen readers.		Yes	https://github.com/loisfraga/craftpy/	All	(i) increasing the number of diagrams types; (ii) optimizing the interface for better compatibility with smaller screens; and (iii) enhancing the existing diagrams to allow for greater versatility and the addition of more elements.	Academia
Educational chatbot on Data Structures and Algorithms for the visually impaired	Vidhish Panchat, Lakshmi Kupip	2023 5th Biennial International Conference on Nascent Technologies	2023	Short (6)	English	Unnamed Tool	Speech-based educational chatbot in web application	Informal tool testing	Zero	Help visually impaired people as well as normal students many concepts regarding data structures and algorithms.	A chatbot that is voice-enabled as well as multilingual. It can interact with more than 180 global languages, although in the paper, they focused on the Hindi language.		Not available	-	Not Specified	Include making the conversation more personalized for the user.	Academia
Growing an Accessible and Inclusive Systems Design Course with PlantUML	Sarah Caruthers, Amber Thomas, Liam Kaufman-Wills, Aaron Wang	SIIGSE 2023: Proceedings of the 54th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education	2023	Full (7)	English	PlantUML	Text-based UML diagramming tool	Adaptation of a course for blind students	One blind student	Permit the student to read, create, and edit UML diagrams using their screen reader.	Extend previous efforts to make diagramming accessible for blind students in an undergraduate course, by finding an adaptation that fully included a blind student in a team project and peer feedback activities that relied heavily on diagramming.		Yes	https://openplantuml.com/	All	-	Academia